

ISic1476

I.Sicily inscription 1476

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Helorus

Place of origin (modern)

Eloro

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644986

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 57.0870

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1951.0256

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 100 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Calderone, S. 1949. Iscrizione agonale di Heloros. *Epigraphica*. 10: 146-149.
Manganaro, G. 1963. Nuove ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. *Siculorum
Gymnasium*. 16: 51-64. At 56
Cordiano, G. 1997. La ginnasiarchia nelle "poleis" dell'occidente mediterraneo
antico. *Studi e testi di storia antica* 7. Pisa. At 49

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